

Synthesis of some 1-[5'-Aryl-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl]-3-chloro-4-substituted-2-azetidinones as Potential Fungicides

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The thiadiazole compounds perhaps by virtue of incorporating thiosemicarbazide framework and -N=C-S- linkage¹ possess pesticidal activities². The biological potency of β -lactam rings has been well realised. In view of this and encouraged by the satisfactory performance of some thiadiazolyl-2-azetidinones³ incorporating aryloxy moiety at position-5 of the thiadiazole ring, we considered it worthwhile to continue our investigations on some azetidinones incorporating various substituted thiadiazole moieties.

The required 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (2a-h) were prepared essentially by cyclodehydration of appropriate 4-arylaceto-thiosemicarbazide (1a-h) with concentrated H₂SO₄ by the reported method⁴. The condensation of 2a-h with aromatic aldehydes in methanol furnished compounds 3a-h, which were converted to the title compounds (4a-h) by cyclocondensation with chloroacetyl chloride in dry dioxane in presence of Et₃N (Scheme 1). The ir band of the compounds at 1710-1680 cm⁻¹ and ¹H nmr signal of ring protons of the 2-azetidinone ring at δ 4.3 and 5.1 confirmed the presence of β -lactam structure.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) on a Varian EM-360 (60 MHz) spectrometer. Satisfactory elemental analyses (C, H, N) were obtained for all the compounds.

2-(*p*-Methoxybenzylidene)amino-5-(*p*-chlorophe-

nyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (3d) : A mixture of 2-amino-5-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (2d; 0.01 mol) and *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in methanol using glacial acetic acid as catalyst was refluxed for 5 h. The excess of methanol was distilled off and the residue was poured into water. The solid separated was crystallised from aqueous ethanol (3d; 70%), m.p. 185-87° (Found : C, 58.11; H, 3.48; N, 12.90. C₁₆H₁₂N₃OCl requires : C, 58.27; H, 3.64; N, 12.75%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1630 (C=N), 1630, 1520 and 1460 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ring); δ 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.8 (1H, s, -CH=N-) and 7.5-8.2 (8H, m, ArH).

Other compounds (yields 65-85%) were prepared similarly : 3a, m.p. 195-96°; b, 175-76°; c, 156-57°; e, 175°; f, 216°; g, 162-63°; h, 210°.

1-(5'-*p*-Chlorophenyl)-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl-3-chloro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-2-azetidinone (4d) : A solution of chloroacetylchloride (0.012 mol) in dry dioxane was added dropwise below 10° to a well-stirred solution of 2-(*p*-chlorobenzylidene)-amino-5-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.03 mol). The solution was stirred for 6 h, then excess of dioxane removed and the residue was poured into water. The resulting solid was washed and crystallised from chloroform-hexane (2080)(70%), m.p. 147-48° (Found : C, 53.10; H, 3.09; N, 10.20. C₁₈H₁₃N₃O₂SCl₂ requires : C, 53.20; H, 3.20; N, 10.34%); ν_{\max} 1700 (C=O) and 1640 (C=N); δ 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.3 (1H, d, CH), 5.1 (1H, d, CHCl) and 7.0-8.0 (8H, m, ArH).

Other compounds (yields 53-71%) were prep-

- 3,4 a; R = H, R' = Cl e; R = 4-OCH₃, R' = 4-Cl
 b; R = 2-Cl, R' = 4-Cl f; R = 4-OCH₃, R' = 4-OCH₃
 c; R = 4-Cl, R' = 4-Cl g; R = 2-CH₃, R' = 4OCH₃
 d; R = 4-Cl, R' = 4-OCH₃. h; R = 4-NO₂, R' = 4-OCH₃

Scheme 1

ared similarly : **4a**, m.p. 165°, **b**, 148–50°; **c**, 180–83°; **e**, 130°; **f**, 168–70°; **g**, 167°; **h**, 213–15°.

Fungicidal screening :

Cultures of the test fungi *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* were obtained from Botany Department, University of Gorakhpur. The antifungal activity of compounds **4** was evaluated against *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* at concentrations 1000, 100 and 10 ppm by agar-growth technique. The number of replications in each case was three. The results were compared with the commercial fungicide carbendazim using the same dosage.

The fungicidal activity data of most of the compounds indicate significant toxicity at 1000 ppm concentration against both the fungi. The presence of *p*-chlorophenyl group at C-4 of the azetidinone skeleton and at C-5' of the thiazidazole ring endowed strong antifungal effect (**4c** : 95% inhibition against *A. niger* and 80% against *H. oryzae*). Other compounds showed the following % inhibition : 81–95% for **4a**, **b**, **d**, **f–h** and 70% for **4e** in comparison to 98% for carbendazim (control) against *A. niger*; and 68–80% for **4a–h** in comparison to 94% for carbendazim (control) against *H. oryzae*.

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